

Conventional microfinance in Morocco: Mission drift practices?

Hamza ABOUCHATIR

PhD student, INREDD

Faculty of Law and Economics

Cadi Ayyad University, Marrakesh

Hamza.abouchatir1@gmail.com

My Omar ESSARDI

PES, INREDD

Faculty of Law and Economics

Cadi Ayyad University, Marrakesh

Omar_essardi1@yahoo.fr

Abstract:

Lifting poor people from abject poverty was the *raison d'être* of microfinance schemes in Third World (TW) countries. As the most recent literature has recognized, although ups and downs in achieving poverty alleviation, microfinance institutions have economically worked well in operating microcredit, the aim of uplifting the living standard and generating incomes of their unbankable clients has not been generally met as some empirical studies had shown mitigated impacts. Then, microfinance was questioned for its effectiveness theoretically and empirically leading the majority of researchers to investigate the hidden part of the microfinance Iceberg' effect. Our study aims theoretically and through secondary data to reveal economic fundamentals theories of the microfinance movement as well the main factors behind the unsuccessful experience of microfinance in Morocco since 2008 (the crisis of microcredit) which matches clearly with claims of international agencies about its mission drift. Last, we suggest the implementation of Islamic microfinance through the ijarah forward contract as a new approach for financing poor people and for reliable empowerment of poor families and micro-entrepreneurs

Keywords: Microfinance, poverty, theory, practice, Morocco.

Received: 25 July 2022, **Accepted:** 29 September 2022

Citation : Abouchatir H., Essardi M.O, (2022), Conventional microfinance in Morocco: Mission drift practices?, *Researches and Applications in Economics and Management Sciences*, Vol 1, No 1, pages : 1-20.

Introduction

Poor and poverty are commonly used words among academicians, international organizations, and politicians in the TW countries. From the inception of life, Poverty was an ancient human civilization's social and economic problem. A huge number of researchers were published around the world to understand the main factors of its expansion and then suggest possible strategies and policies to overcome it. In the eighteenth century, societies used to encounter their financial needs via different informal credit and cooperative lending methodologies (Armendariz and Morduch, 2005). Nor of those initiatives was accepted internationally since the 1970s, microfinance come as the name of revolutionary approaches with the accessibility of the poor to credit without assets for collateral, enough financial records, and credit history to increase their productivity in the self-employed economic activities for reducing vulnerability and poverty. Microfinance means “*programs that extend small loans to very poor people for self-employment projects that generate income in allowing them to take care of themselves and their families*” (Microcredit Summit, 1997). It mainly targets low and medium-income communities that reside in emerging economies where rates of financial penetration are low compared with the developed countries (Chiu, 2017).

With thousands of MFIs operating worldwide, some critics addressed the framework of MFIs claiming that most of them are drifting away from their initial mission of reaching out to the poor and empowering women to enhance their financial performance through making outstanding profits (Quayes, 2020). This would be obvious as the majority of MFIs target no-pro poor people, by exercising an ‘iceberg’ effect which can be seen as utopic as it runs far ahead of the reality –microfinance in which the visibility and profile of the forefront of the debate, backed by its powerful proponents conceals the vast array of approaches and interventions that do not conform to microfinance promise as defined by Morduch (1999).

This paper aims to investigate mission drift intentions in Moroccan microfinance market using data source from Mix Market database and a literature review about the mission drift and impact studies of MFIs on poverty reduction in the Moroccan context.

Our paper is unique in the Moroccan context as we systematically review the theoretical foundations of microfinance through a literature review on the concept, its origin, its evolution as well as the major approaches that have focused on the issue of microfinance and past relevant studies about different approaches of defining it, rather than take a traditional description of Moroccan microfinance system without a solid analysis of its theoretical background. Hence, the causality between major economic theories and subsequent failures of MFIs in Morocco was unexplored.

The rest of our paper is organized as follows. In the first part, we emphasize the confusion related to microfinance and microcredit concepts, followed by the second part, where we review theories which explain the ‘Mission drift’ intentions of MFIs: psychological and economic factors. In the third part, we present the Moroccan microfinance landscape. Last but not least, we highlight evident issues in the Moroccan microfinance system that conforms perfectly with theories analyses and suggest an alternative ethical mode of micro-financing.

1. Definitions of microfinance and microcredit

The evolution of concepts was characterized by many historical economic development strategies that tend to better solve economic and social issues of poor people in marginalized areas especially poor rural households. In a response to these particular issues, microcredit programs are seen as financial intermediaries and anti-poverty instruments which can cater to the needs of many low-income countries (Khandker, 2005).

Microcredits are small loans conceptualized for financially excluded and underprivileged individuals in low-income countries. The first microcredit experiences have been lost over time due to the lack of institutionalization of their credit formula, but modern MFIs have their roots in the 1970s in Bangladesh when Muhammad Yunus granted 27 dollars to 42 women to help them finance their small businesses. Afterward, microcredit gained large popularity and became Buzz-word among researchers, international agencies, and organizations worldwide. Unfortunately, numerous empirical studies showed controversial impacts of MFIs programs on poor communities.

The declaration of the microcredit summit held in Washington DC in 1997 defined microcredit programs as those "extending small loans to poor people for self-employment projects that generate income, allowing them to care for themselves and their families". The declaration also stated that "in most cases, microcredit projects offer a combination of services and resources to their clients in addition to the credit for self-employment. These often include savings facilities, training, networking, and peer support" (Microcredit Summit, 1997). "Financial services for the poor" refers to microfinance and other financial products for the underserved lower-income segments of the population (Imboden, 2005). Another definition of microcredit, it is usually associated with: (a) very small loans, (b) no collateral, (c) the formation of borrower groups, (d) borrowers from among the rural and urban poor, (e) loans for income generation through market-based self-employment, and (f) privatization, generally through the mechanism of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO) control over disbursement and determination of the terms and conditions attached to each loan (Swaminathan, 2007).

Armendariz and Morduch (2005) define microfinance as additional efforts beyond microcredit to 'collect savings from low-income households (LIHs), and in some places to help in distributing and marketing clients outputs'. Particularly, they base this distinction on three key factors – the service (s) provided; the focus in terms of clients and objectives; and the providers of these services. In general, microcredit often refers to the provision of small loans to impoverished groups of people for self-employment to foster entrepreneurship, particularly targeted at unbanked women due to the stringent requirements and conservative practices of the formal financial sector. Various financial schemes around the world bear resemblance to microcredit, although the Bangladesh experience popularised the practice worldwide. For example, 'Susus' in Ghana, 'Chit Fund' in India, 'Tandas' in Mexico, 'Arisan' in Indonesia, 'Cheetu' in Sri Lanka, 'Tontines' in West Africa, and 'Pasanku' in Bolivia display similarities and have been operating for several decades (CGAP, 2006). Below we sort a list of financial products and services provided by modern MFIs worldwide.

Table 1: Summarized financial products of MFIs (Conventional and Islamic)

Credit	Savings	Insurance (Takaful)	Others
Term loan	Compulsory savings	Health	Mobile
Entrepreneurs Loan	Flexible Savings	Life	subscription
Housing Loan	Daily savings	Property	Mobile
Health and sanitation	Voluntary Savings	Credit	financial
Seasonal	Time deposit	Crop	services
Education	Fixed Deposit	Others	Inward
Disaster	Risk fund		remittance
Consumption			services
Loan top-up			Micro-leasing
Mid-term loan			Asset-transfer
Emergency loan			
Migration loan			
Islamic microfinance loan (PLS, Mark-up, and Interest-free loans)			

Source: Adapted and modified from Mia et al, (2017)

1.1. Microcredit and microfinance: Functional differences

Microfinance is defined as a development approach that provides financial as well as social intermediation (Ledgerwood, 1999; Robinson, 2002). Financial intermediation includes the provision of savings, credit, and insurance services, while social intermediation involves organizing citizens' groups to voice their aspirations and raise concerns for consideration by policymakers and develop their self-confidence through training, soft skills, entrepreneurship skills, and more.

These services are provided by three types of lenders: formal institutions, such as rural banks and co-operatives; semi-formal institutions, such as NGOs; and informal sources such as moneylenders and shopkeepers. Institutional microfinance includes microfinance services provided by both formal and semi-formal institutions, collectively referred to MFIs (Asian Development Bank, 2004). The basic functional difference between microcredit and microfinance programs concerns the type of service that they provide. The former, such as Grameen, provide mainly one kind of service loan distribution and recovery - which is linked to group formation and compulsory savings. Micro-finance programs, on the other hand, provide all kinds of financial services, including micro-credit. Thus micro-credit is a necessary, but not sufficient element of the new financial sector that seeks to cater to the credit needs of the poor who do not have access to formal sources. Besides microcredit, MFIs provide other financial services namely: microsavings, microinsurance, and remittances. This is perhaps the reason why the microfinance movement is described as the second revolution in credit theory and policy (Woller, 2002).

The first revolution concerned microcredit and was focused on overcoming the structural barriers to providing savings and credit services to the poor. These barriers include information asymmetries, lack of collateral, high cost, high risk, and systematic market bias.

Table 2: Functional differences between microcredit and microfinance concepts

Functional differences		
	Microcredit	Microfinance
Type of MC suppliers	NGO	microfinance institutions
Type of service	microcredit	microcredit, savings, micro insurance, remittances
Type of intermediation	financial intermediation	financial and social intermediation
Principal motives	social purposes, charity	profit-oriented

Source: Adapted from Elahi and Rahman (2006)

1.2. Microcredit and microfinance: Conceptual differences

There are two fundamental conceptual differences between microcredit and microfinance. The first concerns the financial goal. NGOs or non-profits that run microcredit programs do not, by definition, seek large profits. Microfinance, however, is a for-profit private venture with a profit-oriented maximization approach. The second fundamental conceptual difference concerns how the operations are financed. Microcredit programs that are run by non-profits depend upon external finance (International donors and organizations), but microfinance programs need to self-finance their activities without external aid.

Table 3: Conceptual differences between microcredit and microfinance concepts

Conceptual differences		
	Microcredit	Microfinance
Reliance on subsidies	External funds	Self-financing activities
Principal motives	Social purposes, charity	Profit-oriented

Source: Adapted from Elahi and Rahman (2006)

2. Microfinance and micro-credit: Defining micro-intermediation approaches

MFIs using the minimalist approach normally offer only financial intermediation, but they may occasionally offer limited social intermediation services. Minimalists base their approach on the premise that there is a single “missing piece” for enterprise growth, usually considered to be the lack of affordable, accessible short-term credit, which the MFI can offer. While other “missing pieces” may exist, the MFI recognizes its comparative advantage in providing only financial intermediation. Other organizations are assumed to provide other services demanded by the target clients. This approach offers cost advantages for the MFI and allows it to maintain a clear focus since it develops and provides only one service to clients.

The minimalist approach that proposes microcredit was shown to increase poor communities' access to credit, enable risk mitigation and strengthen social ties. However, in a randomized control trial evaluation, microcredit also led to lower subjective well-being and fewer entrepreneurial activities (Karlan and Zinman, 2011).

The integrated approach takes a more holistic view of the client. It provides a combination of a range of financial and social intermediation, enterprise development, and social services. While it may not provide all four, the MFI takes advantage of its proximity to clients and, based on its objectives, provides those services that it feels are most needed or that it has a comparative advantage in providing. MFI chooses a minimalist or more integrated approach depending on its objectives and the circumstances (demand and supply) in which it is operating. If an MFI chooses to take an integrated approach, it should be aware of the following potential issues:

- Providing financial and nonfinancial services are two distinct activities, which may at times lead an institution to pursue conflicting objectives.
- It is often difficult for clients to differentiate “social services,” which are usually free, from “financial services,” which must be paid for, when they are receiving both from the same organization.
- MFIs offering many services may have difficulties identifying and controlling the costs per service.
- Nonfinancial services are rarely financially sustainable (Ledgerwood, 1999).

An integrated approach to microfinance has four types of impact on poor communities - economic, political, social, and cultural (Zohir and Matin, 2004). The economic benefit accruing from MFI is to increase the liquidity of credit by lowering transaction costs and providing employment opportunities. MFIs also provide social services and strengthen social bonds through solidarity within groups as part of their social component. The political impact of MFI is achieved when members participate widely in representative elections, influence policy, and mobilize for rights. Integrated MFIs also influence cultural mores through strengthening the belief systems and norms.

3. Institutional Approach and Welfarist Approach : (Minimalist and Maximalist impact approaches)

The institutionalist or financial market approach characterizes the ideology that prevailed during the 1990s, a period of great popularity for microfinance. The main objective of MFIs was to achieve financial viability to ensure their survival. This is consistent with the institutionalist view that an MFI's priority is to ensure its financial sustainability by becoming financially self-sufficient. The institutionalists' thesis is based on the idea that microcredit will never make a real difference to the general level of poverty in the world if its operations depend on subsidies (Dugas-Irena, 2007).

The institutionalists' approach puts the MFIs at the center of interest. The focus is solely on the financial health of the MFI at the expense of the clients. The "best practices" guide developed by the institutionalists refers only to standards that can improve the financial performance of MFIs, and does not refer to the practices that MFIs should have concerning

their clients. This guide was designed to standardize these practices at the international level. Its adoption is seen as an essential step toward achieving financial self-sufficiency and access to capital markets (Morduch, 2000). The institutionalist approach has gained increasing power and is supported by international organizations such as the World Bank, the United Nations, USAID, CGAP, etc. Its advocates aspire to have their vision recognized as the most effective and legitimate one for MFIs to fulfill their social mission.

The welfarist approach, described by Woller et al, (1999) considers MFIs as institutions whose sole and principal mission is to fight poverty. This approach emerged around 1998 (Dugas-Irena, 2007) as a response to the various concerns of professionals and theorists about the practices of some MFIs, which were considered irresponsible and excessively commercial. This approach focuses on poverty measurement, which has led to its recognition as a poverty measurement school (Asselin and Anyck, 2002). For the proponents of this approach, in contrast to the institutionalist vision, MFIs should not seek financial performance at all costs, which risks diverting them from their social mission; they can survive without being financially self-sufficient. By diverting microfinance from its ideological foundations, the quest for financial performance would be a brake on innovation and poverty reduction (Roy, 2006).

To decide what approach is effective, we need to measure its impact on poor people alongside the financial viability of MFIs. This is how we can justify the transition from an institutionalist approach to a welfarist approach. Traditionally, minimalist impact studies appeared in the mid-1990s, when microfinance activities first appeared in the world. This period was marked by a great deal of interest in the question of the financial profitability of MFIs. Following the bankruptcy of some MFIs and the dependence of others on financial subsidies granted by donors, impact studies emphasized the "capacity of institutions to operate in such a way as to cover their operational and financial costs while allowing their clients to benefit economically from the services offered" (Jeannin and Sangare, 2008).

This minimalist approach, also known as an institutionalist, believes that the financial independence of MFIs depends on their ability to increase the number of clients and achieve high repayment rates. The social aspect is not taken into account in this approach, nor is the question of the adequacy of services and products offered and their impact on clients. This approach considers that high repayment rates indicate client satisfaction with the services offered.

The studies that emerged from this maximalist approach, known as the welfare approach, came about as a result of the limitations of the first generation of studies, particularly about the neglect of the social aspect in the evaluation of the effects of microfinance. While the first-generation impact studies sought to evaluate the income effect as an indicator of the success of MFI programs, the second generation was concerned with explaining the gap between the financial and social objectives of MFIs and their adequacy with the results obtained. This approach puts the client at the center of interest. It seeks to analyze and explain the reasons for clients in dropping out or experiencing difficulties with microcredit programs. As a result, the focus has shifted from the size of the client and credit portfolio favored by the minimalist

approach to the adequacy of client needs and services offered, as well as to the targeting of poor clients.

To maintain a good image and thus meet the expectations of donors and investors who are more sensitive to the issue of social responsibility, MFIs have turned to achieve social objectives. Thus, the look for social performance became a major issue for MFIs, which committed themselves to reporting on their social commitments via external audits and to transmitting information to be evaluated by rating companies that assigned ratings according to social commitment.

4. Economic analysis of microfinance failure

Microfinance is emerging as an integral part of the new development paradigm, described by the phrase "participation and development." Although the idea has become quite popular among donor agencies, development practitioners, and academicians, theoretical premises on which this idea is founded seem entirely unexamined. Also, microinsurance as part of microfinance products offers a range of services to poor and non-bankable people.

Accordingly, this article investigates the academic merits, as well as potential consequences, of this popular poverty alleviating model from the supply side perspective and asks a provocative question: Do the microfinance ventures have features that suggest that the establishment of this new finance industry in the Third World countries might further complicate their pervasive poverty problems? The answer to this question appears affirmative to be affirmative. First, the microfinance idea is founded on two theoretical premises, both of which are very controversial. Second, the lack of microcredit is not the cause of the third world's deplorable poverty situation--a fact that suggests that the supply of microcredit cannot alleviate poverty in these countries. Finally, the promotion of microfinance ventures in the Third World has the potential to create private groups, which have vested interests in perpetuating their prevailing poverty situation, especially in capitalistic systems. Elahi and Danopoulos (2004) suggest that critical evaluation is needed to judge the academic virtue of microfinance theory.

Microfinance as a part of the financial global system aims to carry about the financial needs of very poor people and seek for financial performance to cover operational costs and other relevant costs to sustain its activities. Moreover, the nature of the system to which almost of TW countries belongs is capitalism. From an academic perspective, this system is manipulated by human motives for undertaking economic activities.

This debate goes back to Adam Smith's theories, articulated in two of his masterpieces – one philosophical and the other economic. The philosophical work, the Theory of Moral Sentiments, is an inquiry into moral psychology, which concerns the nature of moral judgment (Smith, 1984). According to Smith, the source of moral judgment lies in the concept of sympathy. No matter how selfish human beings are, they have an innate interest in the fortunes of others, although they may derive no gain other than the pleasure of seeing another's good fortune. Thus human nature includes such qualities as the compassion that we feel for the misery of others, whether we witness it directly or are made to imagine it.

The economic treatise, *An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*, on the other hand, argues that human selfishness is the key to material progress in the non-communist state. These seemingly incompatible perceptions of human nature remain the subject of academic debate (Tribe 1999; Witztum 1998), suggesting that one needs to be very careful when ascribing human motives in making an intellectual analysis. Besides this historical debate, the current literature shows tremendous interest in the issue. Smith's theory, often described as *homo economicus*, underlines human selfishness as appropriate economic behavior. However, sympathy or altruism is empirically observed as an essential element of human nature, as shown by the existence of charitable organizations.

Both economic and psychological factors undermine the capacity of MFIs as a component of the financial system, to alleviate poverty and prove their excessive cupidity to profit maximization independently of poor people's economic situation. For his part, Yunus (1998) is promoting the idea of 'social' capitalism that is driven by social goals. He succeeds to put his idea into practice despite many problems and political resistance. He believes that social entrepreneurs who benefit from microcredit loans can indirectly promote the consumption, production, and wealth of diligent people in TW countries. The issue with Yunus's perspective contradicts the practice of major MFIs that applicate excessive interest rates and other unjustified costs. In brief, there is a serious problem with the source of financing not the output of working beneficiaries.

Figure 1: Theoretical background of the critical analysis of conventional MFIs paradigm

Source: Author's schematic

5. Mission drift aspects of MFIs

Over the past decade, international agencies and donors like ACCION International stated that subsidization is only needed in the first phase of the introduction of an MFIs program. For the next life cycle process, MFIs should take a commercial approach to be self-sustained (Ghosh

and Van Tassel, 2008). On the other hand, some critics argue that this strategy may shift away MFIs from their original mission of poverty reduction.

Starting with the normal position of MFIs towards its mission of poverty alleviation and economic empowerment of poor people especially rural women. To meet these social and economic objectives, MFIs provide small loans to needy people either by progressive high credit ceilings to the existing borrowers with high repayment records. Or by cross-subsidization, which consists of reaching out to wealthier clients to finance indirectly and increase the size of the average loan given to small borrowers (Mosley, 1996; Armendariz and Morduch, 2005; and Cull et al. 2008).

Mission drift was also defined as a remarkable increase in MFI's average loan size to wealthier clients for other purposes rather than progressive lending or cross-subsidization (Armendariz and Szafarz, 2009). Mission drift can be observed through two proxies: average loan size and interest rates charged by MFIs (Armendariz et al. 2011).

Thus, mission drift may arise when MFIs choose to target the not-very poor people and crowd out poor people because of such great advantages when serving the former segment. It can only appear when the poverty alleviation purpose is forgotten by MFIs policies. Another definition of “mission drift” occurs as the phenomenon where “... microbanks moved away from serving their poorer clients in pursuit of commercial viability” (Cull et al. 2007). Sometimes increasing the average loan size may be explained by several factors without being far from poverty alleviation promises such as strategic policy and the lending behavior of customers (Christen, 2000).

The vast majority of the literature shows controversial impacts of MFIs, some studies such as Hulme and Mosley (1996), Coleman (1999), and Copestake et al. (2005) find that the wealthiest clients were well served by MFIs than the poorest people. Otherwise, Khandker (2005) conducts a study on the impact of microfinance in rural Bangladesh, he found a positive impact on the poorest of the poor people which is higher than those in moderate poverty levels.

6. Landscape of microfinance in Morocco

Since its inception, The first small loan programs that finance the economic activities of low-income people began in 1993-1994. However, it was not until 1996 that local microfinance experience began to be known in the country (Bensaid et al, 2017). Indeed, before the microfinance crisis in 2008, the sector is outperforming expectations and reflected this evolution in several aspects, namely the main financial indicators: the number of clients served, loan outstandings, the portfolio at risk, and the size of the land.

Though, Data about these indicators start to be available in 2005 proving that Microfinance institutions are not fully interested at the beginning of their financial performance data transparency. Moreover, we remark that none of the social indicators was included in their Data access such as (poverty line tool measurement or the number of poor clients served ...) which means that Moroccan MFIs try to hide their social mission intentions and give a neutral impression of classic microbanks with a fully profit-oriented market approach. The same

observations were noted by Diani (2019) validating the absence of information transparency from MFIs about their activities and the high similarity of MFIs' framework to conventional banks.

A microfinance institution initially called by Moroccan regulators as ‘microcredit Association’ is an organization that provides financial services (Microcredit, remittances, micro-insurance, micro-savings) to people excluded from the traditional banking system. Indeed, the law that governs microfinance in Morocco has introduced 13 specialized associations that represent the sector. These include AL AMANA, ATTAWFIQ, AL BARAKA, ZAKOURA, AL KARAMA AMSSF, ATIL, FCA, AIMC, AMOS, INMAA, AGIMCE, and AMAPPE.

Figure 2: Evolution of the number of active borrowers (from 2005 to 2017)

Source: MIX Market¹

It has been nearly 12 years since the term “microfinance crisis” first appeared in the context of Morocco. Up until then, the microfinance sector in the country started to recover rapidly its performance one year after the crisis. Since then, we have seen a full inversion of the activity and a change in client perceptions about the efficacy of micro-credit to enhance their living quality. It’s time to set things right. Of course, Morocco had a crisis in 2009 but it was far way different from other MFI crisis experiences in some countries (IFC, 2014). The microfinance crisis was dominated by the collapse of Zakoura, a badly mismanaged institution that pursued breakneck growth while amplified by poor lending methodologies and grossly inadequate systems.

¹ **MIX market** is an international provider of MFIs data exchange about social and financial performance indicators and about different actors of the sector.

As we can see, above in Figure 2, the number of clients served by Zakoura MFI in 2009 was negatively impacted due to the crisis, as consequence, Zakoura MFI was factored out and removed from the list of Moroccan active MFIs. Mainly, the microfinance sector is composed of two regulators of the working system namely: BANK AL MAGHRIB and the Ministry of Finance. We note also, that the Mohamed VI center for support and solidarity to microfinance provides financial assistance to MFIs as a lender of last resort besides to USAID AFD² and JAÏDA Banks³.

There is a huge difference between associations in terms of size and institutional capacity today. Indeed, the state of the sector shows that the activity is driven by three big associations as we will discover later (Figure 3) :

- Al Amana: Established in 1996, one of the leaders of the microfinance sector in Morocco, the largest in terms of portfolio size and the number of borrowers, the institution was created with the technical assistance of the American NGO Vita and the support of USAID.
- Attawfiq microfinance: is a not-for-profit association created by the Banque Populaire group for the distribution of loans excluded from the banking system, it owns 32% of the turnover of the sector.
- AL Baraka Foundation: Established in 1996, (FONDEP-Salaf Albaraka), is a not-for-profit association that now finances 20% of the micro-enterprises addressed by the sector in Morocco with a portfolio of assets of more than 20% One billion dirhams.

Figure 3: The structure of MFIs in Morocco

Source : Bensaïd et al. (2017)

² USAID AFD : AFD and USAID cooperate at the operational level, notably on projects related to water stress in Jordan and in the health sector in Haiti.

³ JAÏDA Banks : is a financing fund for microfinance institutions (MFIs) in Morocco. It was established as a limited company under Moroccan law and approved by the central bank of Morocco (Bank Al Maghrib) as a financing company.

7. Impact of microcredit on poverty alleviation in Morocco

The most effective tool for assessing the benefits of a microcredit program is the measurement of its impact on the poor in terms of employment, income, consumption, assets, net worth, nutrition, contraceptive use, fertility, and children's schooling. The immediate impact of having access to credit from a microcredit program is on employment and, consequently, income.

The induced income and employment effects may have an impact on other outcomes such as consumption, nutrition, contraceptive use, fertility, and education. In addition, asset accumulation and hence household net worth may increase incomes generated from self-employment are sufficient to cover the costs of participation. But identifying the credit impact is problematic because of: (a) fungibility of credit; (b) non-randomness in program participation; and (c) non-randomness of program placement.

Since the launch of microfinance in Morocco, several AMC's as well as various agencies have launched studies on the sector (Table 4) to know its real impact on poor people.

Table 4: Impact studies of microfinance program in Morocco

Title of the paper	Author	Year	The purpose of the study	General findings
Impact Study of the Zakoura microcredit Program	Fouzi MOURJI	2000	To evaluate the impact of microcredit loans on poor households' lives and businesses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An increase in customers' income compared to non-clients. - The Customers appear to be better protected against the shortage of inputs, compared with the non-clients without extra- financing. - the boost of entrepreneurship - professionalism and project guidance. - More access to school and education than a control group.
Evaluation of the impact of Microfinance in Morocco	IKM (Impact, Knowledge, Market)	2005	The objective of this study was to assess the impact of microcredit	The whole sector targets principally women (68% of clients) and rural poor households.

			on beneficiaries (households and entrepreneurs) and to evaluate the AMC market (supply and demand)	microcredit has a significant positive impact on income level, investment, and employment. High satisfaction and perception towards microfinance sector.
Study of the economic and social impact of microcredit	Institution Albaraka (FONDEP)	2014	Estimate the impact of Albaraka services on the customers at several levels (financial performances, personal and professional development, the well-being of the household, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The loan allows for an increase in the micro entrepreneur's income. -the seniority of the customer allows to increase the monthly profit by 60% during the first two years and to double this benefit after two years. -Increase the total household income for old and new customers. -Improvement of the housing conditions after obtaining the loan at Albaraka. -Reduction in the average length of the Hungry period to about three months.
Evaluation of the impact of microcredit in a rural area in Morocco: the case of Al Amana institution	French Agency of Development in partnership with Al Amana institution and the Paris School of Economics	2012	The objective of the study is the evaluation the impact of the Al Amana microcredit offer on agricultural and non-agricultural activities,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The borrowing rate is relatively low and highly variable from one village to another; -The offer of microcredit has an impact on the development of existing activities, mainly concentrated

			household incomes and assets, the level of poverty and food safety as well as the place of the women in the household.	in agriculture and breeding. This development is translated by a generation of agricultural income, diversification of owned livestock, and an increase of savings in kind in breeding. -The offer of microcredit has no impact on the creation of new activities.
--	--	--	--	---

Source: Author’s table

8. An alternative microfinance model for social performance in Morocco

International experience has shown that the Islamic or conventional microfinance sector guarantees its existence under perfusion independently of any external subsidy. The international experience has shown that the Islamic or conventional microfinance sector has been able to sustain itself on a life support system, independent of any external subsidy, except for the funds provided free of charge by benefactors. Although there is a mosaic of models and programs developed in Islamic microfinance, our reflection in this paper is limited to the famous model of Obaidullah (2008), which perfectly describes the social mission of MFIs toward the poorest people while making some slight modifications that could clarify it, with some slight modifications that may clarify its expected role in social inclusion and development.

The basic sources of funding for this process originated from free funding in the form of funds collected from waqf, qard hassan, and zakat, which are subsequently drained to the needy under several Islamic financing formulas (3P products and commercial products). It remains to be seen that any damages inherent to the activities financed are mainly covered by Islamic ‘Takaful’ insurance.

The proposed model provides financial intermediation through the collection of funds from agents with the financing capacity to lend them to needy agents. In addition, it provides social intermediation through the continuous training of beneficiaries on entrepreneurial culture and the promotion of the principles of solidarity, fraternity, and social cohesion strongly advocated by Islamic law.

Our contribution to this model arises from the incorporation of the ijarah forward contract for the financing of health and education services, pillars of social development, and inclusion. This lease agreement seeks to provide citizens with full access to health and education services in return for payment over some time. Of course, the quid pro quo imposes heavily on the ability

of the poorest to repay their loans. However, the main advantage of philanthropic sources could offset some of these colossal charges and provide the necessary financial support without harming the financial performance of the MFIs.

As a matter of course, in addition to the traditional financing operations of the MFIs, a part of the funds collected should be given free of charge as Sadaqah. Apparently, from a theoretical point of view, the feasibility factors are met and call for the active support of the main social actors in Morocco and internationally, namely: the future participatory (or Islamic) microfinance institutions, the social state, donors, and international organizations, to put this funding program into practice. This renewal of the model has a more inclusive structure than the basic one. We should note that some papers in the Moroccan context encourage the integration of Zakat, and Waqf to provide the financially excluded people proper services that are Shariah compliant and in respect to their convictions (Zarfi, 2019).

Figure 4: Adjusted IMF model for an effective social development

Source : Adapted from Obaidullah (2008)

Conclusion

In Morocco, conventional or classic microfinance was striking to help poor people overcome poverty and create self-employed entrepreneurs. Thus, based on theoretical evidence, conventional microfinance which is based mainly on interest to generate profits, and which is mainly in line with the principles of capitalism would not be able to meet microfinance goals in TW countries such as Morocco. In this context, our paper suggested an alternative approach to financing which is more inclusive and costly effective to cover the deficiencies and limits of the classical financing paradigm. Our new proposed model integrated Ijarah forward contract, an Islamic product that can enhance the sustainability of the existing model of MFI

(Obaidullah's MF integrated model) by covering the financing shortcomings of poor people for easy access to educational and health services in the Moroccan context. Moreover, the theoretical background used in our study shows some evidence about mission drift practices of Moroccan MFIs from the objective of social performance.

However, we need to prove such mission drift practices empirically by using regression models or simulations to assess the role of microfinance and or validate theoretical assumptions about the mission drift of MFIs in Morocco and test the validity of our proposed model by using both methodologies (qualitative and quantitative).

In our study, we suggested the implementation of Islamic microfinance philosophy to achieve financial and social inclusion of the excluded people from the traditional banking system and microfinance Moroccan network. Indeed, the Islamic industry exhibits more social services and social projects to achieve social and economic development by ensuring equitable redistribution of wealth.

We conclude by noting that the theoretical evidence in this research seems to suggest that Islamic microfinance practices if adopted efficiently, may contribute to serving many key aspects of social and financial inclusion of poor people. We further advise Moroccan regulators, to establish independent Islamic microfinance institutions while it is possible in a primary step to combine Islamic banks' framework with microfinance practices through the SPV mechanism of channeling funds.

We lastly conclude by mentioning some limitations that may affect the accuracy of the findings. First, the research methodology may be considered a limitation since theoretical assumptions may be considered less incredible and hypothetical in the absence of empirical validation. Thus, it would be difficult to generalize such observations to all MFIs. Third, the sole absence of data about microfinance performance during the last decade may not be an ideal factor of transparency delinquency. In terms of recommendations, we suggest that further research on the mission drift of Moroccan MFIs, adopt empirical methodologies to assess their real impact on poor segments of the population. Also, we recommend future contributions to study external and internal factors of mission drift pressure on MFIs which may derive intentionally, from various factors (political, cultural, organizational ...).

References

- Armendariz, B., and Morduch, J. (2005). *The economics of microfinance*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Armendariz, B., and Szafarz, A. (2011). *On Mission Drift in Microfinance Institutions*, *The Handbook of Microfinance*, pp. 341-366.
- Armendariz, B., D'Espallier, B., Hudon, M., and Szafarz, A. (2011). *Subsidy Uncertainty and microfinance Mission Drift*, CEB Working Paper, 11/014.
- Asian Development Bank (2004). *Microfinance: Financial Services for the Poor*. Available at: www.adb.org/Microfinance (retrieved 15 January 2022).

- Asselin, L., and Anyck, D. (2002). *Mesure de la pauvreté : un cadre conceptuel*. Document de travail de l'atelier régional de formation sur la mesure et le diagnostic de la pauvreté. Libreville.
- Bensaid, A.M., Faris, H. and El Hachloufi, M. (2017). *Microfinance in Morocco : State of art*. *Journal of Finance and Investment Analysis*, 6(2), 45-58.
- CGAP (2006). *The new vision of microfinance: Financial services for the poor*. CGAP UNCDF Donor Training.
- Chiu, T. (2017). *Factors Influencing Microfinance Engagements by formal financial Institutions*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 143(3), 565-587.
- Christen, R.P., (2000). *Commercialisation et dérive de la mission des imf la transformation de la microfinance en amérique latine*. CGAP, *Etudes spéciales*, n5, 24p.
- Chui, T.K. (2015). *Factors influencing microfinance engagement by formal financial institutions*. *Journal of Business*, 143, 565–587.
- Coleman, B.E., (1999). *The impact of group lending in northern Thailand*. *Journal of Development Economics*, 60, 105-141.
- Copestake, J., Dawson, P., Fanning, J.P., McKay, A. and Wright-Revolledo, K, (2005). *Monitoring the diversity of the poverty outreach and impact of microfinance: A comparison of methods using data from Peru*. *Development Policy Review*, 60(1), 703-723.
- Cull, R., A. Demirgüç-Kunt, and Morduch, J. (2008). *Microfinance meets the market*. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper Series N° 4630*.
- Diani, A. (2019). *Logique d'acteurs et régulation dans le champ de la microfinance marocaine : vers une commercialisation croissante*. *Revue Recma*, 4(356), 104-119.
- Dugas-Irena, S. (2007). *Le débat entre institutionalistes et welfaristes en microfinance*. Canada: C-A Poissant de recherche sur la gouvernance et l'aide au développement.
- Elahi, K., and Danopoulos, C. P. (2004). *Microfinance and Third world development: a critical analysis*. *Journal of Political and Military Sociology*, 32(1), 61-77.
- Elahi, K., and Rahman, M.L. (2006). *Micro-Credit and Micro-Finance: Functional and conceptual differences*. *Development in Practice*, 16(5), 467-483.
- Ghosh, S. and Tassel, E. (2008). *A model of mission drift in Microfinance institutions*. Working Papers, Department of Economics, College of Business, Florida Atlantic University.
- Helms, B. (2006). *Access for all: Building inclusive financial systems*. World Bank Publications - Books, the World Bank Group, number 6973, December.
- Hulme, D. and Mosley, P. (1996). *Finance against poverty*. London: Routledge.
- Imboden K., (2005). *Building inclusive financial sectors: The road to growth and poverty*. *Journal of International Affairs*, 58(2) ,65-86.
- International Finance Corporation (IFC) (2014). *Ending the microfinance crisis in Morocco: Acting early, acting right*. Washington, D.C. available at: <https://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/5172c485-b2d9-4c7d-af58>.

- Jeannin, P., and Sangare, M. (2008). La microfinance: Quels impacts économiques et sociaux? Communication au 14ème Colloque national sur la recherche en IUT, (p. 9). Lyon: Université Claude Bernard.
- Karlan, D. and Zinman, J. (2011). Scoring for impact evaluation microcredit in theory and practice: Using randomized credit. *Science*, 332(6035), 1278-1284.
- Khandker, S. R. (2005). Microfinance and poverty: Evidence using panel data from Bangladesh. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 19(2), 263–286.
- Ledgerwood, J. (1999). *Microfinance handbook: An institutional and financial perspective*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- Mia, M.A., Lee, H. A., Chandran, V.G.R., Rasiah, R. and Rahman, M. (2019). History of microfinance in Bangladesh: A life cycle theory approach. *Business History*, 61 (4), 703-733.
- Microcredit Summit (1997). Declaration and plan of action. Available on <https://www.mycreditsummit.com/declaration.htm> (retrieved 13 January 2022).
- Morduch, J. (1999). The Microfinance promise. *Journal of economic literature*, 37 (4), 1569–1614.
- Morduch, J. (2000). The microfinance schism. *World Development*, 28(4), 617–629.
- Mosley, P. (1996). The metamorphosis from NGO to commercial bank: The case of Bancosol in Bolivia. In David Hulme and Paul Mosley (eds.) *Finance Against Poverty*, London: Routledge.
- Obaidullah, M. (2008). Introduction to Islamic Microfinance. *The Islamic business and finance network*.
- Quayes, S. (2020). An analysis of the mission drift in microfinance. *Applied Economics Letters*, 28(15), 1310-1316.
- Robinson, M. (2002). *The Microfinance revolution: Sustainable finance for the poor*, Washington, DC: World Bank.
- Roy, D. (2006). La participation et l'appropriation dans l'utilisation de la microfinance. http://www.er.uqam.ca/nobel/ieim/IMG/pdf/DannyRoy_microfinance2.pdf.
- Smith, A. (1984). *The Theory of moral Sentiments*. Edited by D. D. Raphael and A. L. Macfie. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 9-43.
- Swaminathan, M., (2007). The Microcredit alternative? *Economic and Political Weekly*, 42(13) ,1171–1175.
- Tribe, K. (1999). Adam Smith: critical theorist? *Journal of Economic Literature*, 37(2), 609-632.
- Witztum, A. (1998). A study into Smith's conception of the human character: Das Adam Smith problem revisited. *History of Political Economy*, 30(3), 489-495.
- Woller, G. (2002). Introduction to the second microfinance revolution: creating customer centred microfinance institutions. *Journal of International Development*, 16(2), 1-5.
- Woller, G. M., Dunford, C., and Woodworth, W. (1999). Where to microfinance? Draft paper.
- Yunus, M. (1998). Poverty alleviation: is economics any help? Lessons from the Grameen Bank experience. *Journal of International Affairs*, 52(1), 47-65.

- Zarfi, A. (2019). The integration of Awqaf, Zakat, and Crowdfunding in Islamic Microfinance Framework: Focus on Moroccan case. *Researches and Applications in Islamic Finance*, 3(1), 43-57.
- Zohir, S. and Matin, I. (2004). Wider Impacts of microfinance institutions: Issues and concepts. *Journal of International Development*, 16(3), 301-330.